

A TECHNIQUE FOR MICROANALYSIS OF MATRIX AND
FIBER-MATRIX INTERACTION DURING COMPOSITE DEFORMATION

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Summary

Composite materials deform inhomogeneously, necessitating an experimental technique capable of determining strain on a local basis. Response of matrix and interfacial regions to loading and deformation due to crack growth are examples of experimental information of value to the understanding of composite materials. This paper describes how the stereoimaging technique is useful in the study of composite materials. Stereoimaging allows determination of displacements, strains and stresses at the surface of the composite with a spatial resolution down to submicron. Analyses of deformation around fatigue crack tips growing in graphite reinforced epoxy and boron fiber titanium alloy matrix are used to illustrate the application of stereoimaging to composite materials.

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Introduction

The stereoimaging technique is capable of deriving strains within an area a few micrometers on each side. The technique has been used extensively in studying the growth of fatigue cracks through ingot and powder metallurgy alloys. This paper illustrates uses of stereoimaging in characterizing the deformation of composite materials.

Stereoimaging is a technique by which in-plane displacements may be measured on an extremely localized basis (1). From the gradient of these displacements, three elements of the symmetric strain tensor may be computed (2).

Composites are materials purposely designed to be inhomogeneous on a microscopic scale. This is the basis on which their interesting properties are developed, but this also makes experimental investigation of their deformation and fracture modes extremely difficult. A high spatial resolution method is required to discern differences in mechanical response between the matrix and strengthening particles or fibers, and to investigate the interfacial region between the two. Stereoimaging has sufficient resolution to provide the required information.

Description of the Technique

Visualization of Displacements

The stereoimaging technique uses the visual system (eyes and brain) to compare two photographs of the composite made at two different times. The simplest sequence to consider is the comparison of photographs made prior to and after application of load to a crack growing through the composite. Displacements in the axis of the eyes caused by this loading may be seen when the two photographs are placed in a stereoviewer, as illustrated in Figure 1. Displacements in the plane of the photographs are visualized as the third dimension. In other words, the resulting image appears as three dimensional because of the interpretation of the displacements by the brain, but in actuality only in-plane displacements are seen. Deformation fields are nearly always biaxial, particularly, those in inhomogeneous materials, and it is necessary to rotate the photographs 90 degrees to view the deformation along the orthogonal axis.

Two photographs of a crack in a carbon reinforced epoxy composite are shown in Figure 2. The photograph on the left was made at minimum load, and the one on the right was made at maximum load. Both photographs were made in a loading stage which fits into the specimen chamber of a scanning electron microscope (3).

Measurement of Displacements

If displacements can be seen in a stereoviewer, they also can be measured using the techniques of photogrammetry developed for aerial map making. A parallax bar, labeled "P" in Figure 1, is used to set a dot, which appears to float near the surface visualized, onto the surface. This is accomplished by adjusting the length of the bar using a micrometer screw. The concept is illustrated in Figure 3. Displacements are measured relative to a particular (reference) point on the surface. The distance between these points is shown as x_0 in Figure 3. This point may be arbitrarily chosen, or chosen because of its relative position to some feature, such as a crack. The reference point was chosen in Figure 3 to be directly ahead of the crack tip

Figure 1 - Viewing of photographs made at different times in stereoviewer to visualize displacements caused by loading. Measurement of displacements is by parallax bar (P).

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 - Crack tip region in a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite photographed in SEM loading stage. (a) 29N. (b) 99N.

Figure 3 - Schematic diagram illustrating the use of the parallax bar P to measure displacements Δx from the photographs.

and along the line of the crack, so that the motion of material is seen from the viewpoint of a remote observer. For the condition illustrated in Figures 1 and 3, the right side of the crack is observed as lower because $\Delta x > 0$, and the left side is seen as higher because $\Delta x < 0$. To measure displacements in the other orthogonal axis, it is necessary to rotate the photographs by 90 degrees. (In practice, equipment exists which allow both displacements to be determined simultaneously).

Displacements determined from the photographs of Figure 2, as measured by the method described above, are shown in the diagram of Figure 4. Note that this diagram has two scales. The scale of the displacements given on the right side of the figures is different from that of the measurement points which is noted on the left. If both scales were equal, displacements would be difficult to see on the scale of the spatial distribution of measured points.

One of the principal advantages of the stereoinaging technique comes from the fact that no grids or marking points on the material are required for visualization or measurement of displacements. Because a surface, rather than a point, is constructed by the visual system, displacements may be measured at any point desired on that surface.

To gain the high resolution shown in Figure 4, it is necessary to obtain photographs under high resolution conditions and at high magnification. This is necessary because photogrammetric equipment has a maximum limiting accuracy, as with any measurement tool. Actual accuracy depends upon the quality of the photographs and training of the photogrammatrist in addition to the accuracy of the equipment. For the resolution shown in Figure 4, it is necessary to use specimens with carefully prepared surfaces in connection with the loading stage for the SEM.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 - Displacements measured from the photographs of Figure 2 (a) coarse grid and (b) fine grid. Note that the spatial scale (left) is different than the scale of displacements (right).

Determination of Strains

Strains are obtained by computing gradients of the displacements. Since the displacement fields are biaxial, it is necessary to make measurements in both x and y along a regular array of points, so that cross derivatives may be computed. The large displacement definition of strain is used for computations because it has been found that displacement gradients near cracks are often large; thus, the small displacement definition underestimates the strain. The definitions used are shown in the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \\ \epsilon_{yy} &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \\ \epsilon_{zz} &= -(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) \quad \text{constant volume}\end{aligned}$$

Strain out of plane (ϵ_{zz}) may be computed by assuming constant volume for large plastic strains. With this assumption, a total of four elements of the symmetric strain tensor may be determined.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} & \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xy} & \epsilon_{yy} \\ & & \epsilon_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

For the crack tip region of the composite of Figure 2, the coordinate strains ϵ_{xx} and ϵ_{yy} , and the shear strain γ_{xy} are shown in Figure 5. With these strains, a Mohr's circle construction may be used to determine the maximum and minimum principal strains and the maximum shear strain (2). Figure 5(d) shows the maximum shear strains derived from the coordinate strains of Figures 5(a-c).

Measured displacements may be used directly for the accurate determination of crack opening displacements. In general, mixed mode crack opening has been observed for fatigue cracks in unreinforced metals (4,5); this again emphasizes the necessity for making measurements in two orthogonal axes.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5 - Strains near a fatigue crack in graphite reinforced epoxy. Area covered is the fine grid region shown in Figure 4(b). (a) ϵ_{xx} , strain in the loading axis; (b) ϵ_{yy} , strain perpendicular to the loading axis. Crack is shown schematically on the plane of zero strain. x and y scales are in micrometers.

Figure 5 (Continued) - Strains near a fatigue crack in graphite reinforced epoxy. Area covered is the fine grid region shown in Figure 4(b). (c) γ_{xy} , shear strain; and (d) maximum shear strain. Crack is shown schematically on the plane of zero strain. x and y scales are in micrometers.

Use of Stereoimaging for Composites

The micromechanics of fatigue crack growth through Ti-6Al-4V reinforced with continuous fiber boron carbide coated boron has been studied in considerable detail (6,7). This study required good spatial resolution, but displacements were measured with a lower resolution than illustrated in Figures 4 and 5 because a lower resolution was sufficient.

The situation illustrated is shown in Figure 6. The crack tip is approximately 20 μm from an unbroken interface between the boron fiber and matrix. The material has been very carefully prepared so that the location of this interface is known. An interface phase forms between the fiber and matrix, and is noted as "I" on the photograph. Matrix was removed until this structure was revealed; thus, as the fatigue crack was grown, it was possible to know both where the crack was, relative to the fiber, and to know that the interface had not been broken.

For the graphite reinforced epoxy of Figure 2, positions of the fibers are not known, and this makes determination of the effect of fiber reinforcement on the failure mechanism of the composite difficult to determine. The great advantage of the analysis of the crack shown in Figure 6 is that the position of the fiber and state of the interface are known.

Two different analyses were made of the region shown in Figure 6. The first compares a photograph made of this region at minimum load and with the crack remote to this location with a photograph also made at minimum load but after the crack had grown into the field. This no-crack vs unloaded-crack comparison allows the net deformation accumulated by the many intervening cycles to be determined and compared to the deformation which occurs on one loading cycle, the other analysis made of this region.

Figure 6 - Fatigue crack in Ti-6Al-4V approaching an unbroken interface (I) with a B_4C coated B fiber.

The net accumulated strain parallel to the loading axis and the fiber (ϵ_{xx}) is shown in Figure 7(a). Net strain perpendicular to the fiber (ϵ_{yy}) is shown in Figure 7(b), and the accumulated shear strain and maximum shear strain are shown in Figures 7(c) and (d), respectively.

Net strains caused by the crack, Figure 7, may be compared with those caused by the maximum cyclic load shown in Figure 8. Strain in the load axis (ϵ_{xx}), Figure 8(a), is slightly tensile at the crack tip, while the net accumulated strain, Figure 7(a), is compressive. Strain perpendicular to the fiber (ϵ_{yy}) due to the cyclic load, Figure 8(b), is, surprisingly enough, mainly compressive between the crack tip and the fiber, and the accumulated strain is also compressive in the same region. There is, however, a fairly rapid increase in strain at the interface between matrix and fiber caused by the cyclic load. Shear strain caused by loading of the specimen is somewhat larger, Figure 8(c) than the net accumulated value, Figure 7(c), and this trend is approximately the same for the maximum shear strain. Comparison of Figures 7(d) and 8(d) indicates that application of the load causes the maximum shear strain at the crack tip, and along the fiber interface, to increase and become more uniform.

Discussion

The great advantage of the stereoinaging technique is that the in-plane strain tensor may be determined with very great spatial resolution. Either accumulated strains or incremental strains may be determined, which is, potentially, very useful for the study of the fatigue failure of composites. The main disadvantage of the technique is that it is a surface technique only, while in composites, some of the most interesting events may be taking place subsurface. Thus, while the technique offers some capabilities otherwise unobtainable, care must be used in its application.

Application of stereoinaging to the study of composite matrix-fiber interactions is best accomplished when location of the fiber is known, Figures 7 and 8; otherwise, the information developed is difficult to interpret, Figure 5. Not only must careful specimen preparation be used so that the location of the fibers is known, the region of observation must have sufficient features present for the surface to be visualized when photographed through the appropriate microscope.

In addition to strains, it is also possible to compute stresses from the strains, if the proper constitutive equation is known (8). For the titanium matrix alloy, the cyclic stress-strain curve could be used to compute stresses from the measured strains. The stress computation gives three elements of the in-plane stress tensor, the principal stresses and the maximum shear stress. Thus, for a single material location it is possible to determine 12 components of stress and strain.

The ability to effectively use the information gained from composites by application of the stereoinaging technique lags our capability to generate the data. What is the criterion by which the matrix-fiber interface fails, is it due to a critical normal stress or strain, or a critical shear stress or strain? Is the accumulated strain or the cyclic strain of greater importance, for the case of fatigue crack growth? With stress and strain information gained in the highly local region of the fiber-matrix interface, it is at least now possible to pose these questions. Perhaps accumulation of experimental data on a variety of composites, together with attempts to explain that data, will spur further theoretical developments, and, ultimately, better composite materials.

Figure 7 - Fatigue crack in Ti-6Al-4V interacting with B_4C coated boron fiber. Net accumulated strain due to presence of crack. x and y scales are in micrometers. (a) ϵ_{xx} , strain in loading direction; (b) ϵ_{yy} , strain perpendicular to loading and fiber direction. Crack tip is $20 \mu\text{m}$ from fiber interface (see Figure 6), which is indicated on the diagrams by the heavy line.

Figure 7 (Continued) - Fatigue crack in Ti-6Al-4V interacting with B_4C coated boron fiber. Net accumulated strain due to presence of crack. x and y scales are in micrometers. (c) γ_{xy} , shear strain; and (d) maximum shear strain. Crack tip is $20 \mu m$ from fiber interface (see Figure 6), which is indicated on the diagrams by the heavy line.

Figure 8 - Fatigue crack in Ti-6Al-4V interacting with B₄C coated boron fiber. Crack tip is 20 μm from fiber interface. Strains shown are due to the difference between minimum and maximum cyclic load, applied $\Delta K = 22 \text{ MN/m}^{3/2}$, $R = 0.1$. (a) ϵ_{xx} , (b) ϵ_{yy} . Compare with Figure 7.

Figure 8 (Continued) - Fatigue crack in Ti-6Al-4V interacting with B₄C coated boron fiber. Crack tip is 20 μm from fiber interface. Strains shown are due to the difference between minimum and maximum cyclic load, applied $\Delta K = 22 \text{ MN/m}^{3/2}$, $R = 0.1$. (c) γ_{xy} , and (d) γ_{max} . Compare with Figure 7.

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